
Investigating the Insulation Potential of Oyster Mushroom (Pleurotus Ostreatus) Mycelium as a Thermal Insulating Material

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ABSTRACT

The rise in extreme heat caused by the depletion of the ozone layer and increased air pollution is a serious concern that affects both households and the environment, leading to higher energy consumption for cooling. The researchers focused on addressing this issue by investigating the potential of the mycelium of oyster mushroom as thermal insulation panel and being utilized on households. Specifically, *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) mycelium was utilized to create the thermal insulating panel. The research investigates the benefits and feasibility of mycelium-based insulation for various people, including homeowners, rural communities, the environment, engineers, construction suppliers, students, and future researchers.

The study includes several stages including, designing and visualizing the panels, preparing materials and equipment, prototype development, product construction, and assembly of the mycelium-based insulation, alongside with temperature and humidity monitoring, with calculations of density, heat index, and humidity conducted to assess the effectiveness of the panels in reducing heat transfer. The results of the study showed that the mushroom panels were effective in reducing heat transfer by 3-6°C. This means that they can effectively keep households cool. Moreover, the study emphasizes the eco-friendliness of mycelium-based materials, as it utilized agricultural waste and mycelium, contributing to reduced carbon emissions and promoting sustainability in construction practices.

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CHAPTER I

The Problem: Rationale and Background

Background of the Study

The rise in extreme heat is a significant issue in our modern world, impacting both households and the environment. With houses directly exposed to the sun, they feel the full force of this heat. Unfortunately, air pollution had led to the depletion of the ozone layer, which played a crucial role in shielding us from the excessive heat. Since the damaged ozone layer can no longer effectively absorb the heat, the current experience of the full impact served as a reminder that the heat faced today is a direct consequence of human activities that destroy the environment.

Traditional insulation materials, such as polyethylene, commonly used in the Philippines, also raise environmental concerns due to their carbon footprint and the emission of toxic chemicals during its production process. Polyethylene is a type of plastic that is widely used in daily life, such as in shopping bags, plastic bottles, milk jugs, films, and toiletry bottles. It is chemically stable, non-biodegradable, and elastic thus posing serious problems when it accumulates in the environment. Most polyethylene waste, about 79%, is sent to landfills where it slowly undergoes a natural light oxidation process due to exposure to the sun's warmth and ultraviolet rays. This process caused the release of additives from the polymer into the environment, creating greenhouse gases that contributed to global warming and ozone depletion.

Mushrooms have long been studied for their insulating properties in nature. In a study conducted by David Nield (2023) entitled "Mushrooms Seem to Be Able to Regulate Their Own Temperature", he suggested the inclusion of organic material among insulation options, specifically fungi or mushrooms. It was found in the study the remarkable ability of mushrooms and other fungi to maintain cooler temperatures than their surroundings.

Certain types of mushrooms were recorded colonizing dead wood, creating a network of mycelium that helped decompose the wood and provide insulation to the organisms living within it. The temperature recorded also signifies its potential as insulation as it was recorded

to be 2.9°C cooler than the surrounding air with certain mushroom species being as up to 5.9°C cooler.

Before its exploration as a potential insulation material, mycelium had already been utilized in various fields. Originating from the research in the 1990s by Shigeru Yamanaka, it has been used in dietary supplements for its anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties, as well as in mycoremediation, where it was aided in restoring ecosystems by breaking down contaminants.

Mycelium is a thread-like root structure of mushrooms that is used to create mycelium composites. Mycelium was used in creating mycelium composites which are cultivated inside a mold with lignocellulosic biomass or substrate and water, the mycelium then binds the particles of organic matter together, forming a strong material that takes the shape of the mold. As it spread, it acted as a natural adhesive. The result was a solid lightweight composite that takes the shape of the mold where it was grown. There are number of agricultural wastes that can be used in creating mycelium composites which can be anything from used coffee grounds, hemp, sawdust, rice and wheat straws making it unique and environmentally sustainable. As the world progresses, mycelium-based materials continue to evolve, emerging as a potential solution to world problems.

The setting for this research study were households and townhouses located in Parklane Country Homes subdivision in General Trias, Cavite, Philippines. The Philippines is a tropical country with a year average temperature of 32 degrees Celsius. Currently, the country is experiencing El Niño or summer season, which affected the weather and made the country hotter. According to *Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical, and Astronomical Services Administration* (PAGASA), temperatures in Metro Manila and other parts of Luzon reach as high as 40 degrees Celsius and as low as 27 degrees Celsius. These extreme temperatures posed a challenge for maintaining comfortable living conditions inside households.

Therefore, there was a need to explore the potential of utilizing the mycelium of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (Oyster Mushroom) as a Thermal Insulating Material in this setting to reduce the effects of the high temperatures.

According to Zhang et al., 2021, it indicates that Mycelium mixed with other materials had gone through the biological processes, including plant extract or any other leftovers from agriculture. These represent a separate, reliable option that provided an independent and dependent means in order to generate different materials that was useful in the future of the construction industry. In this case, our study would be the utilization of mycelium as a thermal insulating material. The mycelium features excellency in its thermal performance. (Zhang et al., 2021). With observation and scientific experiments, it was reported that an average of 2.9 °C (5.2 °F), mushrooms were colder than the surrounding air with a range of uncertainty of 1.4 °C (2.5 °F). This temperature ordinance was discovered accidentally by researchers as they were testing out their thermal camera and suddenly noticed the mushroom developing in the surrounding forests that was found to be colder than the vegetation around it. It was confirmed by researchers that mushrooms regulate through evapotranspiration or releasing water into the air. (Nield, 2023). The utilization of thermal insulation materials improved the efficiency of the energy in the building enveloped and by also reducing thermal loads in hot climate zones (Gauvin and Vette, 2020). The results for the literature review by Al-Qahtani et al. (2023), Mycelium showcased exceptional thermal and acoustic insulation properties owing to its low thermal conductivity and considerable mechanical strength. With the process of heat transfer through walls and roofs through conduction was a significant and important factor in the overall heating load of a building. Effective insulating materials like Mycelium might minimize energy consumption by reducing conduction heat transfer. The utilization of Mycelium-based of Oyster mushroom minimized the overall energy needed for heating.

The mycelium of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (Oyster mushroom) materials, represented a significant step towards achieving sustainability in the construction industry. The mycelium derived from oyster mushrooms holds huge potential in addressing the environmental concerns associated with traditional insulation materials. The versatile application of mushrooms in various products, including bricks, sustainable packaging, sound panels, and speakers, has showcased their versatility and eco-friendly attributes. Within the realm of construction, mushrooms had emerged as a significant in providing sustainable alternatives. The remarkable capacity of mycelium to form robust structures has been demonstrated through the creation of bricks, offering a viable and environmentally conscious substitute for conventional building materials.

The objective of this research was to investigate the use of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (Oyster mushroom) mycelium as a Thermal Insulating Material and the potential environmental benefits of using Oyster mushroom mycelium in the production of thermal insulating materials and estimating the feasibility of using this material.

The overall purpose of this research study was to address the challenges caused by climate change. The study investigated the use of Oyster mushroom mycelium as a Thermal Insulating Material. The product would be developed in response to the need for relief from excessively hot weather conditions.

General Statement of the Problem

This experimental study investigated the mycelium of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) as thermal insulating material utilized on households to reduce heat temperature in households. This was conducted at Parklane Homes General Trias, Cavite during the second semester of the academic year 2023-2024. The study aims to determine the following questions:

Specific Questions:

Specific Objective: To identify the amount of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) spawn and sterilized rice straw needed to develop an effective mycelium-based oyster mushroom insulation material.

1. How much *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) spawn and sterilized rice straw is needed to develop an insulating material that can effectively reduce heat transfer?

Specific Objective: To assess the efficacy of mycelium-based *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) insulating materials in reducing indoor heat temperature within households consistently, with a temperature reduction range of 3°C to 6°C.

1. How does the mycelium-based *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) insulating material consistently reduce the rate of heat in households within the range of 3°C to 6°C?

Specific Objective: To analyze the effect of the thickness of the mycelium-based thermal insulator material in reducing heat experienced in households.

1. How does the 3-inch thickness of the mycelium-based thermal insulating material affect its ability to reduce heat transfer?

Theoretical Framework

Insulation Theory and “*Mushrooms Seem to Be Able to Regulate Their Own Temperature*”

Figure 1: Diagram of the science behind Insulation by Knauf

According to the Infoam Roofing Manual, November (2012), "Heat can be transferred into any object through electromagnetic energy." As each day passes, more heat and radiation could be transferred through roof-top surfaces. In addition, with the implementation of different alternatives for finding solutions to block the flow of heat, utilizing a reflective membrane roof structure or insulation panels. Insulation panels could help reduce heat flow through roof surfaces and block the radiation that flows from the sun into houses. Insulation theory helps the house to protect and keep the heat outside using the conduction method. Insulators absorbed heat to maintain the temperature inside the house.

The heat from the sun circulates around the air, causing heat to rise all around, and could flow from a higher to a lower temperature. When heat is absorbed by an object, its temperature increases, and it surrounds the structure with heat. The transmission of heat could be done by means of conduction, convection, and radiation. These three could transfer

heat through any object or by molecule-to-molecule transmission. In accordance with the theory, the heat flow cannot be stopped and can only be slowed down by the use of insulation or heat-reflective surfaces.

In addition to the insulation theory proposed by Knauf Exeed Insulation LLC and David Nield's findings, house roofs, which were commonly exposed to light, absorbed heat through them. Which caused individuals to buy insulation panels for a more average indoor temperature and to control solar radiation from flowing inside.

A recent study of Yirka, B. B. (2023). He stated that *"mushrooms seem to be able to regulate their own temperature."* With the utilization of pandemic thermal cameras, it captured images showing that the mushrooms are cooler compared to the vegetation around them.

On average, mushrooms were found to be 2.9°C cooler than the surrounding air, with a margin of uncertainty of 1.4°C. Certain mushroom species were recorded as being up to 5.9°C cooler. By exploring different mushrooms and providing details on how they regulate their own temperature, the researchers discovered that the huge amount of water carried by the mushroom structure could cool itself, which is called evaporation. Consequently, this evidence highlights the potential of mushrooms to effectively regulate local environments through their cooling properties. As such, this study was aimed to utilize *Pleurotus ostreatus*, commonly known as the oyster mushroom, as an insulator to investigate its effectiveness in regulating and reducing heat. The data from this theory could help expand the uses of the mushroom's unique ability.

Both theories could relate to each other because they represent solutions and new discoveries that could be used to expand and implement new inventions in solving real-world problems. Therefore, the researchers had utilized oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) mycelium as a thermal insulating material to seek new discoveries and ideas for regulating and reducing heat.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2: IV-DV Model

The pattern of the study shows the relevant variables of the current study and how they relate to each other. The independent variable of the study is indicated to be the oyster mushroom. The dependent variable that is presented in the study is how effective the insulation of the mycelium of the oyster mushroom as a thermal insulator is. The dependent variable was set to be observed by the researchers and was the primary interest of the researchers in this study. The extraneous variables that are identified in the current experimental study were the amount of Oyster Mushroom Spawn, amount of wet rice straw substrate, Temperature reduced by the mycelium insulation, and the thickness of the insulating material.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis: Utilizing the mycelium of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) as an insulation is effective as a thermal insulating material.

Assumptions of the Study:

1. 100 grams of oyster mushroom spawn is sufficient to produce a mycelium composite material that is effective as a thermal insulating material.
2. 400 grams of sterilized Rice Straw Substrate is adequate to produce the mycelium for the material combined with 100 grams of oyster mushroom spawn.
3. The mycelium-based thermal insulation material consistently reduces heat transfer in households by 3°C to 6°C.
4. The 3-inch thickness of the mycelium-based thermal material is sufficient to reduce heat transfer.

Significance of the Study

This experimental research aims to investigate the mycelium of Oyster mushroom as Thermal Insulating Material. Furthermore, this study will be able to provide insights on the production of insulating materials using the mycelium of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom).

Specifically, the study will benefit the following:

Homeowners. They will gain a lot of advantages because the study will be used to keep houses warm or cool, which will save energy, lower energy expenses, make living more comfortable, and help protect the environment.

Rural Communities. Mycelium of Oyster mushroom can be used to create thermal insulating materials which can be constructed to a small scale in communities. It can benefit the households and small businesses by making insulation more accessible to more people.

Environment. Mycelium-based thermal insulating materials is an eco-friendly solution by using agricultural waste and mycelium resulting in reduction in carbon emissions and promoting sustainability in construction.

Engineers. Engineers who build, design, and construct infrastructures are significant benefactors of this research, most specifically Civil engineers and Construction engineers. The utilization of Mycelium of Oyster mushroom is an innovative and efficient product that carries a significant role in their field and sector.

Construction Suppliers. They may be liable with this research study as they can sell the innovative product that is created by the researchers. They may sell the Mycelium-based of Oyster mushroom thermal insulating material.

Students. The study will benefit the students who are undertaking the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand, to gain valuable information and

knowledge in terms of utilizing organic materials in forming industrial and construction materials.

Future Researchers. They may conduct new studies and can make a better invention that is relevant to the current research study. This will serve as reference material that can benefit the community.

Scope and Delimitation

This research study will investigate the ability of *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) mycelium as an insulating material. Past studies of utilizing mycelium in composites have stated that mycelium-based composites have good fire resistance properties and also acoustic insulation properties reducing noise levels. However, the primary focus of the study remains on the development of a thermal insulating material out of mycelium of *Pleurotus ostreatus* oyster mushroom.

This study focuses on the variables related to the mushroom-based insulation. As it investigates the factors concerning the composition of the mushroom insulator, such as its effectivity. The scope of the research is delimited to the *Pleurotus ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) mycelium for insulation purposes, specifically in the context of reducing heat transfer. Other potential applications of mushrooms in other aspects and alternative organic materials for the substrate will not be considered in this study. Additionally, the study does not aim to investigate the broader structure of insulation methods but rather concentrates on the specific use of mycelium as a thermal insulating material. Moreover, this study will focus on the weather and temperature conditions in the Philippines, as it aims to investigate the applicability of *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium-based insulation in that particular context and the application in low-ceiling houses which are common in Parklane Country Homes Subdivision in General Trias, Cavite.

Definition of Terms

Conceptual Definition:

Biodegradable. Capable of being decomposed by bacteria or other living organisms.

Biomimicry. The concept of replicating nature's solutions to solve human problems, by studying and imitating biological processes, structures, and systems.

Carbon footprint. The total amount of greenhouse gases emitted directly or indirectly by human activities, typically expressed in equivalent tons of carbon dioxide.

Cellulose. Large structural chain of body fiber from plants that forms algae and oomcytes.

Global warming. The long-term increase in Earth's average surface temperature, primarily due to human activities such as burning fossil fuels and deforestation.

Lignocellulosic. Materials containing lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose, typically found in plant cell walls.

Mycelium. Thread-like root structure of mushrooms used to create mycelium composites, which are cultivated inside a mold with organic matter and water to form a strong, lightweight material.

Ozone layer. Layer in Earth's stratosphere that plays a crucial role in shielding us from excessive heat by absorbing ultraviolet radiation from the sun.

Polyethylene. Type of plastic material widely used in daily life, including shopping bags, plastic bottles, films, and toiletry bottles.

Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical, and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA). Agency service of the Philippines that informs and updates individuals regarding the country's weather conditions monitored every day.

Operational Definition:

Pasteurization. Partial sterilization of a product, such as milk or wine, to make it safe for consumption and improve its keeping quality.

Thermal Insulation. Reduction of heat transfer between objects in thermal contact or in range of influences of radiation.

Sustainable Construction. Using recyclable and renewable materials in building projects while minimizing the consumption of energy and waste production.

Resource Efficiency. Minimizing the impact on our environment by using the planet's limited resources in a sustainable manner.

Mushroom Cultivation. Process of cultivating mushrooms by their spawn. It is complicated but detailed to grow.

Sterilize. Make free from bacteria or other living microorganisms.

Oxidation. Process or result of being oxidized, which is being combined chemically with oxygen.

Conduction. Process by which heat or electricity is directly transmitted through the material of a substance when there is a difference of temperature or of electrical potential between adjoining regions, without movement of the material.

Insulation. Process of keeping heat, sound, or electricity from spreading.

Organic (Materials). Matter in which it is composed by organic compounds such as plants and animals and their waste products in the environment.

Biomimicry. Practice of making technological and industrial design to copy natural processes.

Compostable Materials. Product that can disintegrate into a non-toxic, natural element. Unlike biodegradable materials, compostable materials break down quickly and completely into soil that can be used to help plants grow.

Agricultural Waste. Unwanted or unsalable materials produced wholly from agricultural operations. They are plant residues from agriculture.

CHAPTER II

Review of Related Literature and Studies

This chapter presents the related literature and studies after the in-depth search done by the researchers. All the gathered related literature and studies will be the foundation for establishing effective research. Additionally, this will also present the synthesis to fully understand the research to be done.

Related Literature

This part provided an overview of related literature that contributes to the Mycelium of Pleurotus Ostreatus as a Thermal Insulating Material. These literatures provided support and served as a reliable foundation for the researchers' investigation.

Foreign Literature

Mycelium-based Bio-Composites as a Sustainable Alternative

According to Ghazvinian (2021), mycelium-based materials offer several sustainable advantages. These materials are produced using environmentally friendly processes, utilizing waste from various industries to minimize environmental impact. Additionally, they are biodegradable, reducing waste accumulation after use, and exhibit lightweight properties, effective insulation, and fire-retardant characteristics.

Mycelium acts as a natural binder, replacing conventional construction materials and finding applications in packaging, insulation, and furniture design. However, literature on mycelium-based bio-composites in the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry remains limited, despite its historical use for industrial purposes dating back to the 1990s. Mycelium-based materials offer a sustainable alternative to petroleum-based insulation materials, providing efficient insulation, fire resistance, and air purification properties for building applications.

Mycelium as a Solution for Building Insulation

Mycelium, which is the root structure of mushrooms, can be used to make walls for sustainable buildings. These walls have been studied extensively and are known for their good insulation and energy performance. Mycelium-based materials are affordable, environmentally friendly, and have a low carbon footprint. They provide insulation from heat and sound and also have good resistance to fire.

Researchers have found that mycelium can be grown from agricultural waste and shaped into different forms like bricks and panels. This makes it a versatile material that can be used for various construction purposes. It's not only used for insulation but also for packaging, furniture, art, and textiles. Overall, mycelium-based composite walls are a sustainable and eco-friendly option for insulation in buildings, making them a promising alternative to traditional construction materials (Fellah, et al., 2024).

Eco-Friendly Mycelium of Mushroom

The literature discusses the innovation of compostable packaging materials made from mushrooms by Ecovative Design. This packaging utilizes mycelium, the vegetative part of a mushroom, and cellulosic agricultural by products to create a compostable and thermal insulating packaging solution. The benefits of this mushroom packaging include being compostable, thermally insulating, cost-effective, and nontoxic. It addresses several UN Sustainable Development Goals related to industry innovation, sustainable cities, and responsible production and consumption. The process involves adding mycelium to cellulosic material, placing it into a mold, allowing the mycelium to bond the substrate together, and then halting growth through a drying process. The resulting product is thermally insulating, water-resistant, and fully home compostable, mimicking natural material cycling processes. (Unknown, 2021).

Local Literature

Rice Hull and Waste Polystyrene Foam as a Composite Material for Insulation

The Philippines faces significant challenges with solid waste management, particularly agricultural waste like rice hulls and polystyrene foam, which are abundant and contribute to environmental degradation. Polystyrene foam, commonly used in packaging, adds to the waste volume without proper recycling or reuse.

In Flores, (2020) study, these wastes were utilized to create an insulation material by shredding the foam to match rice hull dimensions, then combining them with adhesive and molding them. The resulting composite material exhibited excellent insulation properties compared to commercial options. This underscores the potential of using green building materials to develop environmentally friendly composite construction materials, offering promising solutions for the construction industry.

Coconut Fiber as Concrete Reinforcement

Philippines is the second-largest producer of coconut in the world with a quarter of its total land area producing 150 million tons of coconut, but 45% of the coconut husks aren't utilized or left to rot. This gap is what prompted Aquino, et al., (2021) to study utilizing coconut husks in coconut fiber-reinforced concretes to enhance the durability properties where then it can be utilized in construction.

Although the literature doesn't directly correlate with our study about mycelium-based insulation, this signifies that different agricultural wastes are being studied into their potential applications and at the same being develop to either serve as an alternative to current construction materials or simply add a choice for consumers and engineers or other stakeholders. Lastly, the inclusion of the CFRC study highlights the potential of different agricultural wastes in being utilized in construction applications.

Abaca Fiber-based Reinforced Polymer Composite

Abaca fiber also known as "Manila Hemp" is obtained from the stem of the banana family exhibits properties that make it sufficient for various environmental-friendly. Abaca is commonly used in different textiles and handicrafts.

The abaca contains mechanical properties that are comparable to synthetic fibers than other natural fibers can. It also exhibits excellent its high tensile strength and flexural strength attracting different researchers to study it. The study by Paglicawan, et al. (2022) studied its utilization reinforcement for composite materials. The study concluded with the abaca fiber being a good reinforcement material for composite but they suggested further study on stacking sequences like alternating its layers of abaca and glass fibers, to further improved its potential and usage.

While this study doesn't correlate in our study about utilizing mycelium-based insulation material, it offers an insight regarding on the potential of different variations of agricultural wastes and products being utilized on different applications particularly on our study focusing on insulation material which is a construction material. This study also serves as guide to future researchers to focus and think of other potential materials to be used in different applications because all materials have different potential applications.

Related Studies

This part of the study presents ideas gathered from related studies focusing on Mycelium of Pleurotus Ostreatus as a Thermal Insulating Material. These studies provide valuable educational support and serve as a reliable foundation for the researchers' investigation, enriching the readers' understanding.

Foreign Studies

Mycelium as an Alternative Insulation Material

In a study by Robertson, et al., (2020), they create a composite material using different fungal strains which include *Trichoderma asperellum*, *Agaricus bisporus*, *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Ganoderma lucidum* (GL) among others.

But the study focused on *Trichoderma asperellum* and *Agaricus bisporus*, where it was found that both strains showed high moisture resistance and strength, particularly when grown on rapeseed cake. Both strains also showed increased stiffness when subjected to continuous humidity changes.

The study stated different characteristics of mycelium-based composite material that are beneficial for our world which includes, high moisture resistance, sustainability through the use of natural and waste resources and biodegradability. These characteristics the potential of mycelium composites to contribute to environmental sustainability, resource efficiency, and innovation in science (Robertson, et al., 2020). By using this study as a guide in creating mycelium-based thermal insulating material, we can contribute in addressing challenges we face which in this case, we're addressing the heat experienced in households.

Mycelium-Based Thermal Insulation for Cooling Footprint Reduction

The study delved into the potential of mycelium-based materials for sustainable construction and thermal insulation. It revealed promising traits such as reduced thermal conductivity compared to conventional materials like polyethylene foam, along with favorable thermal insulation properties, and potential energy-saving applications in households (Al-Qahtani, 2023).

While recommending mycelium-based composites as eco-friendly alternatives in construction, the authors also highlighted the need for further research to refine production, design optimization, and address challenges related to panel enlargement. This recommendation resonates with our study, which aims to explore mycelium's viability in creating thermal insulating materials. By incorporating these recommendations, we can advance toward developing thermal insulation materials using locally sourced mycelium, promoting innovation and providing an alternative to traditional insulating materials contributing to environmental pollution and global warming.

Composite Panel from Mushroom and Fiber Substrate

The study by Shakir, et al., (2023) focused on the development of a composite panel for thermal insulation using spent mushroom substrate fiber and empty fruit bunch fiber. The researchers investigated the thermal conductivity, flexural strength, and water absorption properties of the composite materials to assess their suitability for insulation applications.

The study found that the sandwich composite panel made of 60% and 40% empty fruit bunch fiber was the optimal ratio, it resulted in decreased thermal conductivity, indicating improved insulation properties and flexural strength which ensures the structural integrity and durability of the insulation material, making it suitable for practical applications in construction (Shakir, et al., 2023).

In relation to our study, the research on the sandwich composite panel and our research on mycelium-based insulation share common vision in having sustainability in households, improving thermal temperature in households, and being environmentally conscious. By using the study as a guide, we can contribute to the development of cheap, eco-friendly and sustainable material that can be utilize not just for insulating but for other purpose that it can be utilize to.

Local Studies

Using Waste in Producing Bio-Composite Mycelium Bricks

One of the major causes of an increase in the consumption of resources is the progress of the construction industry. Although it leads to new technologies, it heavily contributes to global warming. The study by Ongpeng, et al., (2020) conducted a study of creating a composite brick using waste and mycelium as its binding material.

In his study it was noted that the that mycelium acts as a fibrous-binding material, enhancing the compressive strength of the bricks and making them more ductile compared to regular substrate bricks without mycelium. It was also found in the study that the amount of mycelium has a corresponding effect on the brick, increasing its linear dimensional change. The results showed that the use of mycelium led to an increase in strength in compression compared to traditional bricks. The strength of brick was directly correlated with addition of mycelium, acting as bio-composite binder, enhancing the strength and size of the bricks. The study also concluded with the author stating that it's a promising alternative but noted that further research is recommended to further explore the relatively new material in being used in construction industry (Ongpeng, et al., 2020).

Bamboo as Sustainable Building Material

The study of Adier, et al., (2023) was conducted as an exploration on utilizing green building materials, specifically using bamboos. The use of bamboo in the construction industry has shown numerous environmental advantages because of the carbon dioxide reduction compared to conventional structural materials. Bamboo presents physical properties that show its applications in different areas. These properties include its size, dimension, texture, density, moisture content, thermal conductivity, and absorption.

Bamboo being used as a composite material and reinforcement has been long explored. In the study, it was found that using bamboo sticks as reinforcement enhances its strength properties in terms of compression with increase ranging from 3.24% to 20.94%. Other studies also examined the effectiveness of using bamboo fiber as reinforcement material, with findings suggesting an optimal performance of 20%. Heat treatment was also found to enhance the compressive strength of boards composed of bamboo sticks.

In its relation to our study, both bamboo and mycelium are studied and utilized for their sustainability and potential applications in eco-friendly construction. While bamboos are not specifically utilized for insulation, it represents one of the potentials of using different eco-friendly materials into developing composite materials that can potentially revolutionize the construction industry.

Urban Waste for Mushroom Growth

According to Alvarez and Bautista, (2021), the study investigated the feasibility of using urban wastes to cultivate mushrooms near a university in the Philippines. The researchers experimented with various materials including used paper, banana peels, leaf litters, and sawdust. Results showed that some combinations, such as 100% used paper for one type of mushroom and 75% used paper for another, facilitated optimal mushroom growth. Conversely, certain combinations yielded suboptimal results. The study revealed that the choice of materials influenced the speed of mushroom growth, mushroom yield, and even the size of the mushrooms, with some materials producing larger mushrooms with longer stems. Overall, the findings suggest that urban waste materials have potential for effective mushroom cultivation, offering benefits for both food production and environmental sustainability.

Synthesis and Justification of Current Studies

This study aims to investigate the Mycelium of the Pleurotus Ostreatus as a thermal insulating material. The related literature and studies cited by the researchers will serve as the basis for developing and strengthening the current study.

In the related literature, mycelium emerges as a sustainable solution with diverse applications. According to Ghazvinian, 2021 points out its eco-friendly production and versatile properties, showing its potential to reduce harm to the environment while offering lightweight, biodegradable, and fire-retardant materials. Fella, et al., (2024) further discuss mycelium's effectiveness in insulating buildings, highlighting its affordability, eco-friendliness, and adaptability to different construction needs. Moreover, the work of Ecovative Design in creating compostable packaging materials showcases mycelium's versatility and eco-friendliness in solving packaging challenges sustainably. Additionally, the contribution of an unknown author emphasizes mycelium's potential in addressing industry innovation and promoting sustainable practices. Collectively, these studies suggest that mycelium holds promise as a sustainable alternative across various industries, calling for further exploration and innovation to maximize its environmental benefits and resource efficiency.

In line with local literatures, Flores, (2020) investigated the utilization of rice hulls and waste polystyrene foam as a composite material for insulation, addressing solid waste management challenges in the Philippines. Similarly, Aquino, et al., (2021) examined the use of coconut fiber as reinforcement in concrete, aiming to enhance durability properties while reducing waste from coconut husks. Although not directly related to our study on mycelium-based insulation, these investigations highlight the ongoing exploration of agricultural waste for alternative construction materials. Additionally, Paglicawan, et al., (2022) explored the use of abaca fiber as reinforcement in polymer composites, demonstrating the versatility of agricultural products in various applications. These studies collectively underscore the importance of sustainable practices in construction and offer insights into the diverse range of materials that can be explored for environmentally friendly solutions, guiding future research in the field.

In the related foreign studies, the potential of mycelium as a sustainable insulation material is highlighted. Robertson, et al., (2020) and Al-Qahtani (2023)

demonstrated its high moisture resistance and superior thermal insulating properties, while Shakir, et al., (2023) developed composite panels with enhanced insulation and structural strength. These findings underscore mycelium's viability for eco-friendly construction solutions, urging further research to optimize production and scalability. Insights from these studies can accelerate the development of affordable and environmentally friendly insulation materials for various uses in sustainable building and beyond.

These local studies highlight the innovative potential of utilizing waste materials in sustainable construction practices and food production. Ongpeng, et al., (2020) demonstrated the feasibility of creating bio-composite mycelium bricks, leveraging mycelium as a binding material, thus enhancing strength and ductility while reducing reliance on traditional resources. Similarly, Adier, et al., (2023) explored bamboo's use as a green building material, showcasing its structural properties and effectiveness as reinforcement, contributing to reduced carbon footprint in construction. Alvarez and Bautista (2021) showcased the viability of repurposing urban waste for mushroom cultivation, offering a dual benefit of waste reduction and food production. Together, these studies underscore the potential of repurposing waste materials for eco-friendly practices, offering innovative solutions to mitigate environmental impact across various industries. Further research could enhance understanding and application of these sustainable approaches, potentially revolutionizing construction and agriculture sectors towards a more sustainable future.

CHAPTER III

Research Methodology

This chapter illustrates the research methodology and procedures used by the researchers. It presents the research design, instruments, locale, prototype, materials, and all the processes will be done and used all throughout the study.

Research Design

This research is about investigating the utilization of mycelium as a thermal insulating material. The quasi-experimental approach with non-equivalent group design was viewed as the most appropriate design for our study as it will enable us to easily evaluate the effectiveness of utilizing the mycelium of oyster mushroom as thermal insulating material.

The quasi-experimental approach with non-equivalent controlled group design was utilized as it gives us flexibility and control over the experiment. It offers flexibility because it allows us to investigate the thermal properties of a mycelium-based insulation grown under controlled settings. It also offers control because we can exert control over the overall growth environment and material properties of the insulation being made.

The experiment was done with two groups: the control group and the experimental group. The control group is a model simulating a house without any form of insulation inside and the experimental group is a model simulating a house with the mycelium-based insulation material being installed. In the construction of the model, the procedures will be the same to avoid any mismeasurements and fluctuations during the test.

Research Locale

Figure 3: Parklane Country Homes as pinned in Google Maps – A sample house in Parklane Country Homes

This study was conducted at Parklane Country Homes subdivision in General Trias, Cavite, Philippines. This subdivision experience a temperature ranges from 25°C to 35°C making it a representative setting for this study. Parklane Country Homes subdivision is home to the primary beneficiaries of this study which are homeowners. Furthermore, one of the main reasons why this setting was chosen is the convenience for the researchers. Parklane Country Homes subdivision is the nearest and most accessible location for all the researchers, which also possesses the key qualities needed for this research, such as its extreme heat index and the presence of beneficiaries.

Description of the Product

The researchers developed a mycelium-based insulation panels to investigate the possible utilization of mycelium as insulating material. The researchers utilize natural materials such as oyster mushroom (*Pleorutus Ostreatus*) mycelium, rice straw substrate, and flour to develop the composite material.

The insulation panels were produced through a controlled growing process involving the cultivation of oyster mushroom mycelium on a substrate made of rice straw, combined with flour as nutrient. This process utilizes the natural bonding glue-like properties of mycelium, which acts as a binding agent, plowing through the substrate to create solid composite material.

During the manufacturing process, the mycelium was allowed to colonize the rice straw substrate under controlled temperature and humidity, creating a formation of mycelium network that creates a solid material. Once the mycelium has fully colonized the substrate, the panels are harvested and oven-dried, stopping further growth.

The resulting mycelium-based insulation panel took up the shape of the mould it was housed on. The rice straw still looks like before it was inoculated with oyster mushroom (*Pleorutus Ostreatus*) but now with a glue-like layer above it holding the rice straw substrate structure in place. The white spots in the panel are the spawn themselves sprawling out and spreading throughout the panel.

Research Materials

This part of the study presents the materials used by the researchers in order to produce and develop the mycelium-based insulating material and the description of each material.

The Mycelium-based insulation utilized three (3) key materials to grow the mycelium. Firstly, the (1) *Pleurotus Ostreatus* spawn or the Oyster Mushroom spawn, which was bought online on Farmchoice Agribusiness, a store on *Lazada*, an online shopping platform. The spawn is the seed-like material where the mycelium will grow from. (2) Rice straw is another key material in the development of the insulation material because the rice straw will serve as the substrate of the mycelium where it'll grow and will also serve as the backbone or the structure of the whole insulation material. The rice straw was bought from farmers in Salitran at a low price. Another key material is (3) flour, because flour contains carbohydrates that serve as food for the mycelium in growth process. The flour was bought from wet & dry market in Greengate Homes Subdivision.

To house the mycelium, a mold was created using plywood, nails, cling wrap and wood glue. The plywood and nails were bought from a hardware store while the cling wrap was bought on SM Supermarket. The plywood was used as the panel's base and was also utilized as the walls or borders of the panel. Cling wrap was used to seal the plywood and isolate the wood from the mycelium substrate and avoid any contamination.

When handling the mycelium spawn and rice straw substrate, various sanitary tools such as surgical masks and gloves were utilized to avoid contamination and ensure that we won't be harmed during the process. Face masks and surgical gloves were worn to avoid contamination. Sanitary wipes and alcohol were also used to clean all materials that will be used and also ensure cleanliness around the area of the panel creation.

Moreover, the panel also used a humidifier and hygrometer/thermometer which was again bought online through a TREATS SHACK BRAND a store in *Lazada*, an online shopping platform. The humidifier was used to create an environment for the mycelium to grow spontaneously and the hygrometer/thermometer was used to regulate and monitor the humidity and temperature inside the mycelium panel mold.

All these materials and processes created a functional mycelium-based insulation panel that is capable of reducing heat in households while also being eco-friendly.

Procedure in Product Making

The procedures in the development of the mycelium-based insulation consists of designing and visualizing the panel, materials and equipment preparation, prototype development, product construction, assembly of the mycelium housing and the utilization of the mycelium-based insulation. In the design and visualization stage, the researchers determined the appropriate sizing of the panel including its length, width and its thickness based on materials available, amount and intended use. Choosing the most appropriate strain and species of mushroom was also noted during the designing and visualization stage.

Materials and equipment were prepared by buying and gathering necessary materials such as the *Pleurotus Ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) spawn, flour, and rice straw substrate. This stage also included gathering necessary tools such as wood saw, wood glue, metal saw, grinder, wood glue, nails, hammer and cling wrap. The preparation of the mold was ensured to be contamination-free, therefore various cleaning materials were used to disinfect the tools and the materials that were used. In the prototype development stage, we experimented with different amounts of spawn, substrate and flour to formulate a final amount that is the best for growing *Pleurotus Ostreatus* spawn. We also experimented with different growth conditions such as testing for different environments, humidity and temperature.

The product creation is now where all the notes taken down from the prototype development will be used to develop the final product. In the same stage, the assembly was also done where we assembled the panel through layering, with the rice straw substrate, then the spawn and sprinkling flour all over the panel then spraying it with water to moisten the panel.

During the growth process, the panel was observed to maintain the appropriate humidity and temperature because mycelium is very sensitive in terms of growth temperatures. High temperature will enable bacterial growth while low temperature won't enable any mycelium growth.

Prototype of the Product

Figure 4: 3D Prototype Angle (Front View)

Figure 5: 3D Prototype Angle (Side View)

The figures above show the product prototype when applied to houses with low ceilings. The second layer below the roof consists of the mycelium insulating material itself. This is achieved by using a mold containing rice straw as its substrate, combined with oyster mushroom spawn. The growth period for the mycelium typically spans 2-3 weeks. We will not be using the fruiting body of the mushroom instead we will utilize its mycelium, which is the root-like structure of the mushroom. Within 2-3 weeks, the mycelium should have grown within the mold, growing in the rice straw and forming a solid foam-like structure. Insulation panels are commonly utilized in civil and industrial projects, with various types of insulation chosen based on the specific construction project.

Schematic Diagram

Figure 6: Schematic Diagram of the Mycelium Insulation Panel

Figure 7: Schematic diagram of the mycelium at different scales

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized an observational research instrument to observe the mushroom and assess its effectiveness as a heat insulator. This involves systematically gathering data and information by carefully observing and recording details, with the aim of gaining insights and drawing conclusions.

The researchers observed the performance of the mushroom through various experiments, which will include measuring its heat index and density. These experiments were aimed at drawing conclusions regarding the effectiveness of the mushroom. In this case, the researchers decided for this particular instrument to ensure the collection of accurate data regarding the mushroom's properties as a heat insulator.

The observation was first done on the growth of the mycelium on our two final products. The temperature and humidity levels were consistently monitored using a digital hygrometer/thermometer. Temperature and humidity levels were listed down every 5pm in the afternoon for three weeks.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers employed the Observation Method to gather primary data within a controlled environment. Using this method, they controlled a series of variables and carefully documented the results. The observation method was a necessary data collection technique in this scientific study because it involved systematically and carefully observing and measuring results and phenomena within the study's process.

In this case, the researchers focused on investigating whether a mycelium-based insulator material made from the mycelium of an oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) was an effective insulator. To measure this, the researchers experimented to measure several factors: Heat index (the amount of heat the mycelium-based insulator material received), Density (the amount of space the material covered), and Temperature Effectiveness (to test if there was a decrease in temperature when the mycelium-based insulator was installed in an area).

The experiments were conducted by the researchers themselves. They created two boxes: one for a controlled group (without the mycelium-based insulator material) and one for a non-controlled group (with the mycelium-based insulator material) to test whether there was a difference in temperatures inside the boxes. The non-controlled group should have appeared cooler to achieve its objective.

By conducting real-time observations, the researchers were able to identify and directly witness the effectiveness of the mycelium-based insulator material. This conveyed the temperature difference between the two groups, which was crucial for this experiment and study.

By collecting primary data through the Observation Method in this controlled environment, the researchers witnessed the effectiveness of using the mycelium of *Pleurotus ostreatus* as an insulating material. These data could then be analyzed to draw accurate conclusions, make informed decisions, and justify the effectiveness of mycelium-based insulating material.

Treatment of Data

Heat Index

The heat index is used to describe how hot it feels to the human body, rather than just the air temperature. It considers both air temperature and humidity. To solve the heat index, we will utilize a Digital hygrometer and thermometer which both measure the air humidity and air temperature. We will then input our readings on the calculator by the National Weather Service and base the result based on the heat index chart.

Meteorological Conversions and Calculations

Heat Index Calculator

[How do we calculate the heat index?](#)

Choose the appropriate calculator and enter the values. Then click "Calculate".

Using Dew Point Temperature	Using Relative Humidity
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Air Temperature</p> <p><input type="text"/> °F <input type="text"/> °C</p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">Dew Point Temperature</p> <p><input type="text"/> °F <input type="text"/> °C</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="button" value="Calculate"/> <input type="button" value="Reset"/> </p> <p>Heat Index = <input type="text"/></p> </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Air Temperature</p> <p><input type="text"/> °F <input type="text"/> °C</p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: center;">Relative Humidity</p> <p><input type="text"/> %</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="button" value="Calculate"/> <input type="button" value="Reset"/> </p> <p>Heat Index = <input type="text"/></p> </div>

Figure 8: Heat Index Calculator by the National Weather Service

Density

Denser panels offer better insulation by containing more air pockets. We'll calculate the density (ρ) of the sample using the formula: $\rho = M / V$. Here, M is the weight in grams and V is the volume in cubic millimeters.

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V}$$

Figure 9: Density Formula

CHAPTER IV

Results, Analysis and Interpretation

The following chapter presents the results, analysis and interpretation. In presenting the data, the researchers used tables and graphs with the corresponding data of mycelium growth in terms of temperature and humidity and also the results of the tests conducted by the researchers. The tables were arranged according to the observation, each followed by an analysis, interpretation and discussion based on the concepts, principles, and hypothesis.

In our study, we acknowledge that certain tests, specifically thermal conductivity and thermal diffusivity tests through the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) and DOST – ADMATEL (Department of Science and Technology - Advanced Device and Materials Testing Laboratory), were not conducted due to the unavailability of necessary equipment to conduct such tests. This limitation impacts the analysis of our mycelium-based insulation material and its thermal performance.

Despite the limitation, our study focused on other tests that can be conducted to characterize the thermal performance of the mycelium-based insulation, such as the use of a simple hand-held digital thermometer. This approach, while lacking comprehensiveness, will certainly help us make conclusions regarding the possible utilization of mycelium as thermal insulating material.

Results

An insulation panel made from the mycelium of oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*), rice straw and flour as additive was developed by the researchers to investigate and explore the potential of mycelium as an insulating material. The mycelium-based insulation panel was placed in a customized box structure of plywood nailed to each other with the panel inserted inside and directly exposed to the sun to test its effectivity in reducing temperature. After a series of tests, documented results were presented by the researchers.

The production of the mycelium-based insulation material developed by the researchers were tested, experimented, and observed in three (3) consecutive days by the researchers. The experiment was conducted using two constructed boxes measuring the same as the insulation panel itself. There was an experimental box and control box. The mycelium-based insulation was applied in the experimental box and the control box doesn't contain any insulation or covering that may hinder temperature. A digital hygrometer/thermometer with a wired probe was inserted inside the box to record the temperature and humidity inside the box during the experimentation.

According to the data gathered, the mycelium-based insulation panel was able to reduce temperature by 3-6°C as assumed, with it exceeding at some point, reducing the temperature in the insulated box by 7-8°C. The insulated box consistently maintained reduced temperature than the control box. This result was also further proven through density calculation where we got the result of 67.09 kg/m³, confirming the actual experimentation's results about the mycelium-based insulation's effectiveness in reducing heat transfer and maintaining cooler indoor temperatures than the scorching outdoor temperatures exceeding 49-50°C experience by the control box. Simply put, the results signify the effectiveness of the mycelium-based insulation panel and its potential in being utilized in households.

Analysis and Interpretation

One statistical method was used to interpret the results from the actual experimentation. The method of determining Central Tendency; specifically, the arithmetic mean which was used to determine the average values of recorded temperatures inside the insulated box during 3 days of experimentation and the mode of humidity and temperature levels to get the most frequently occurring value observed during the growth period.

Temperature and Humidity

The table below depicts the daily monitoring of the mycelium for three weeks. The table below shows its temperature and humidity per day recorded at 5PM in the afternoon over the course of three weeks.

Date	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (%)
April 7, 2024	32.5	99%
April 8, 2024	30.9	99%
April 9, 2024	33.3	99%
April 10, 2024	34.9	99%
April 11, 2024	32.4	99%
April 12, 2024	30.1	92%
April 13, 2024	33.9	99%
April 14, 2024	32.6	99%
April 15, 2024	34.5	99%
April 16, 2024	34.8	99%
April 17, 2024	34.5	93%
April 18, 2024	34.4	90%
April 19, 2024	34.7	99%
April 20, 2024	33.8	89%
April 21, 2024	32.7	90%
April 22, 2023	33.2	85%
April 23, 2024	34.2	78%
April 24, 2024	35.8	73%
April 25, 2024	34.4	95%
April 26, 2024	33.8	87%

Table 1: Three Week Monitoring table of Mycelium Growth showing its temperature and humidity

Based on the data gathered through three weeks (20 days) of monitoring the temperature and humidity of the mycelium for our mycelium-based insulation, several insights were established on observation on the growth conditions and its potential impact on mycelium growth and insulation performance. The temperature ranged from 30.1°C to 35.8°C indicating that there are varying conditions the mycelium has experienced throughout its growing period. Dates with high temperature i.e. April 24, 2024 (35.8°C) potentially indicates that mycelium experiences stress and affecting its growth that can be attributed with high temperatures. As previously stated, high temperatures have a factor on the growth of the mycelium.

On the other hand, humidity levels ranged from 73% to 99% throughout its growth period suggesting consistent moist environment for the mycelium, which is the most suitable environment for mycelium to grow. However, some days with low humidity level may have potentially impacted the growth of the mycelium as there are some days where the mycelium will slowdown in growth i.e. April 23, 2024: 78%; April 24, 2024: 73%.

During the growth of the mycelium, researchers observed the rice straw substrate where the mycelium was growing became flaky and dry as the humidity dropped. As the humidity dropped, the temperature rose up indicating an external factor such as weather pattern affecting the humidity inside the mycelium panel mold.

Overall, the environmental conditions observed during its growth period shows the importance of closely monitoring the temperature and humidity levels to better optimize the growth of mycelium and its potential insulation performance. Managing these is crucial to have a healthy mycelium and ensure long-term effectiveness of mycelium-based insulation. Analysis on this data would provide deeper understanding into how these factors influence the performance of the insulation material.

Figure 11: Line graph showing temperature over time of the *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium insulator throughout 20 days of growing

Figure 11 presents the daily temperature readings recorded during the three-week monitoring for the growth of the mycelium-based insulation. The data recorded provides insights into the thermal conditions experienced by the mycelium insulation panel over the monitoring period, showing variations in temperature from day to day.

The temperatures throughout the observation period ranged from 30.1°C to 35.8°C indicating that our locale which is Parklane Homes experiences hot weather which is typical in tropical climate countries such as the Philippines. At the same time, during the course of our study we're currently experiencing summer season in the country thus correlating with the temperatures recorded.

Figure 11 shows the trend of the temperature moving like wave indicating consistent high temperatures but also slight fluctuations. The high temperatures peaked at 35.8°C on April 24 indicating consistency of high temperatures. The fluctuations like April 8 and April 24 indicate possible sudden changes in weather conditions.

The lowest peak temperature was recorded on April 12, 2024, with a recorded temperature of 30.1°C. Low temperatures can slow down the growth of mycelium, as it mushrooms prefer warm conditions in growing. However, the temperature of 30.1°C is still within the optimal range for many species of mushroom, so it can be said that it hasn't impacted the growth of the mycelium in major level. On the other hand, the highest temperature was recorded on April 24, 2024, with a recorded temperature of 35.8°C. High temperatures can also affect the growth of mycelium. While mushrooms prefer warm conditions, high temperatures can negatively impact the growth as it'll encourage the growth of other bacteria that will fight with the growth and nutrients intended for the mycelium. The temperature of 35.8°C, while it may look high, is still within the range that's optimal for mycelium growth.

In a study by G P Cikarge and F Arifin in 2018 entitled "*Oyster Mushrooms Humidity Control Based on Fuzzy Logic By Using Arduino ATmega238 Microcontroller*", it was said that optimum oyster mushrooms grow in the 28-30°C temperature range and 80-90% humidity levels. So, when in terms of growth parameters, Indonesia as a tropical country with an average temperature 25-32°C is very suitable for cultivated oyster mushrooms, but for humidity must still be controlled to be fulfilled optimum moisture. The same parameters also apply for the Philippines which has a temperature range 26-30°C which is also suitable for growing oyster mushrooms.

Mode of Temperature Over Time (Growth Period)

The mode of temperature levels identifies the most frequently occurring temperature value recorded during the monitoring period. This statistic is valuable to present the common value during the growing period within the panel. Identifying the mode helps us understand common temperature levels, which is essential for assessing and further optimization of the growth of mycelium.

Temperature (°C)	Occurrence(s)
30.1°C	1 occurrence
30.9°C	1 occurrence
32.4°C	1 occurrence
32.5°C	1 occurrence
32.6°C	1 occurrence
32.7°C	1 occurrence
33.2°C	1 occurrence
33.3°C	1 occurrence
33.8°C	2 occurrences (Mode)
33.9°C	1 occurrence
34.2°C	1 occurrence
34.4°C	2 occurrences (Mode)
34.5°C	2 occurrences (Mode)
34.7°C	1 occurrence
34.8°C	1 occurrence
35.8°C	1 occurrence
32.5°C	1 occurrence
32.6°C	1 occurrence

Table 2: Mode Table of Temperature Levels during the growth period of the *Pleurotus ostreatus*

Table 2 presents the mode of temperature during the growth period of the mycelium. Based on the table, the temperature ranged from 30.1°C to 35.8°C showing variation in the recorded temperature during its growth period. Each temperature recorded has a corresponding occurrence value indicating how many times that specific temperature occurred during the growth period.

The mode temperatures (34.5°C, 34.4°C & 33.8°) indicates that these temperatures were the most frequent occurring values throughout the monitoring period with each temperature occurring 2 times during the experimentation. These observations were commonly observed and represent common thermal conditions experienced within the experimental environment.

Mycelium typically grows best in warm and humid environments. Temperatures recorded in the table fall within the best growing conditions for the mycelium thus supporting the growth of the mycelium. On the other hand, the performance of the mycelium may vary depending on the temperature. This recorded temperature and the mode will certainly help us and future researchers to predict and adjust the performance of the insulation material. According to the research conducted by Zalameda *et al.* (2014), the optimal temperature for cultivating oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus Ostreatus*), using rice straw as a substrate, lies within the range of 32°C to 35°C in tropical climates. No mushroom will fruit if the temperature drops to 20°C. Mushrooms grown at higher temperatures will be smaller and lighter in weight. This research is supported by the Industrial Technology Development Institute (ITDI-DOST) where they listed several species of mushrooms and their optimal growth temperature when being cultivated.

Figure 12: Line graph showing humidity levels of the *Pleurotus ostreatus* mycelium insulator throughout its 20 days of growing

Figure 12 shows the daily humidity level readings recorded during the three-week monitoring for the growth of the mycelium-based insulation. The data recorded provides an overview of the conditions experienced by the mycelium insulation panel over the monitoring period, showing consistent high humidity most of the time with slight variations.

For most of the dates during the growth span, it was observed that the humidity was very high, reaching up to 99%. A humid environment is very common in tropical climates where weather feels hotter than it actually is due to reduced sweating of the human body. There were also slight variations observed where certain dates such as April 12, 17, 20, 23, 24 where humidity is slightly lower than the mode, ranging from 73% to 92%. This indicates that there were weather changes in the environment. The mycelium is like cloudy weather or lower heat than usual leading to lower humidity levels. Towards the end of the month, there was an observed continuous trend in humidity levels, with 73% being the lowest on April 24. This indicates a sudden change in weather conditions during the growth of the mycelium.

Mode of Humidity Over Time (Growth Period)

The mode of humidity levels identifies the most frequently occurring humidity value recorded during the monitoring period. This statistic is valuable to present the common value during the growing period within the panel. Identifying the mode helps us understand common humidity levels, which is essential for assessing and further optimization of the growth of mycelium.

Humidity (%)	Occurrence(s)
73%	1 occurrence
78%	1 occurrence
85%	1 occurrence
87%	1 occurrence
89%	1 occurrence
90%	2 occurrences
92%	1 occurrence
93%	1 occurrence
95%	1 occurrence
99%	12 occurrences (Mode)

Table 3: Mode Table of Humidity Levels of the *Pleurotus ostreatus mycelium insulator* during the growth period

Table 3 shows the frequency of occurrence of humidity levels during the growth period. The mode humidity of 99% indicates that the value was the most frequently occurring value during the monitoring period. A mode humidity of 99% indicates that the environment maintained a high relative humidity for the entirety of the observations. The humidity levels also ranged from 73% to 99% indicating that the environment experiences variations in humidity.

Mycelium also specifically thrives in hot and humid conditions. The recorded number of occurrences (12 times) of 99% humidity indicate that the conditions during the growth period were the best and most appropriate.

Mycelium-based Insulation Panel as a whole

The testing of the insulating materials' effectiveness on thermal insulation was done in a box constructed like a vacuum flask or thermos with the insulation panel directly exposed to the sun, it's also constructed to record the temperature difference between the inner and the outer part of the box. The determination of temperature inside and outside the model building is accomplished by the use of a digital thermometer. It is a pocket-sized, battery-operated apparatus which measures the temperature ranging from -50 to 12000. It consists of a display where the reading is done, and a 2-inch probe whose end is connected to the processor by a 1.5m insulated wire cable.

Temperature Levels throughout the Actual Experimentation

Day	Time	Insulated Box (°C)	Control Box (°C)
Day 1 – 4/29/2024	9:00 AM	38.4°C	53.0°C
	12:00 PM	45.9°C	50.7°C
	3:00 PM	49.4°C	51.0°C
Day 2 – 4/30/2024	9:00 AM	42.0°C	52.8°C
	12:00 PM	41.3°C	52.0°C
	3:00 PM	40.8°C	42.5°C
Day 3 – 5/1/2024	9:00 AM	35.4°C	47.9°C
	12:00 PM	47.9°C	50.6°C
	3:00 PM	46.0°C	49.0°C

Table 4: Table showing the recorded temperature of the Pleurotus ostreatus mycelium insulator all throughout the 3 days of experimentation

Figure 13: Recorded Temperatures of the Insulated Box and the Controlled Box at 9:00 A.M over the course of the 3-day Experimentation.

Figure 14: Recorded Temperatures of the Insulated Box and the Controlled Box at 12:00 P.M over the course of the 3-day Experimentation.

Figure 15: Recorded Temperatures of the Insulated Box and the Controlled Box at 3:00 P.M over the course of the 3-day Experimentation.

Table 4 shows the temperature recorded of the insulated box (insulated with mycelium) and a control box at three different times of the over a three-day period. Let's delve into our observations during the experimentation:

The temperature recorded inside the insulated box was consistently lower than the control box during the three-day experimentation. This is a significant observation that shows the effectiveness of mycelium-based insulation while also demonstrating its potential as thermal insulator.

It was also observed that the temperatures in both boxed (Insulated and Control) has an upwards trend from 9:00 AM in the morning, with temperatures peaking at 12 PM in the afternoon. Temperatures from 3:00 PM in the afternoon is lower indicating the decreasing of temperature as the day progresses. The insulated box also appears to have smaller increase compared to the control box, further indicating the effectiveness of the mycelium insulation in moderating temperature changes.

Variations in temperatures recorded were also observed. For instance, on Day 1, the temperature in the insulated box at 9:00 am is lower than the recorded temperature of 12 pm, with a difference of 7.5°C . Conversely, at 3 p.m., the temperature increased by 3.5°C . The increase in temperature can be attributed to alterations in weather patterns.

On the second day, there was a decline in temperatures within the insulated box. Specifically, at 12 pm, there was a decrease of 0.7°C compared to the temperature recorded at 9 am. Subsequently, at 3 pm, the temperature experienced a further reduction of 0.5°C . These fluctuations in temperature are likely attributable to variations in weather patterns.

On Day 3, the temperatures in the insulated box at all three times are lower than the corresponding times on Day 1 and Day 2. Notably, fluctuations in temperature were observed within the insulated box throughout the day. Specifically, at 12 pm, there was a notable increase in temperature by 12.5°C relative to the reading recorded at 9 am. Conversely, by 3 pm, the temperature had decreased by 1.6°C . These changes in temperature shifts are plausibly linked to alterations in variations in weather conditions.

These recorded observations highlight the effectiveness of the mycelium insulation in maintaining a lower and more stable temperature compared to the control box. We can say that it's effective when installed in actual homes because as seen in our study, it already works in small, controlled boxes.

Mean of Insulated Box Over 3 days of Experimentation

The mean temperature calculated represents the average thermal condition observed inside the insulated box over the monitoring period. By calculating the mean, we obtained a standard measure of typical temperatures experienced within the insulated environment. This helps us understand the overall thermal behavior and effectiveness of the mycelium-based insulation in moderating temperature fluctuations and maintaining comfortable conditions.

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\text{Sum of Values}}{\text{Number of Values}}$$

For 9:00 AM:

$$\text{Values: } 38.4^{\circ}\text{C} + 42.0^{\circ}\text{C} + 35.4^{\circ}\text{C} = 115.8^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{115.8^{\circ}\text{C}}{3} = 38.6^{\circ}\text{C}$$

For 12:00 PM:

$$\text{Values: } 45.9^{\circ}\text{C} + 41.3^{\circ}\text{C} + 47.9^{\circ}\text{C} = 135.1^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{135.1^{\circ}\text{C}}{3} = 45.0^{\circ}\text{C}$$

For 3:00 PM:

$$\text{Values: } 49.4^{\circ}\text{C} + 40.8^{\circ}\text{C} + 46.0^{\circ}\text{C} = 136.2^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{136.2^{\circ}\text{C}}{3} = 45.4^{\circ}\text{C}$$

Below are the mean temperatures of the insulated box at 9:00 AM, 12:00 PM, and 3:00 PM over the three-day period of experimentation.

9:00 AM: **38.6°C**

12:00 PM: **45.0°C**

3:00 PM: **45.4°C**

These mean temperatures provide a general representation of the temperature conditions inside the insulated box at different time points (9 AM, 12 PM, and 3 PM) during the experimentation.

Density

The actual mass density of the insulating material was determined by dividing the average mass in kilograms by the average volume (cu.m.) of the material; $\rho = \text{Mass} / \text{Volume}$ (kg/m³). The actual mass density of the sample was determined based on its actual average mass and dimensions. Below is the solution and interpretation of the result:

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Mass}}{\text{Volume}}$$

$$\text{Length} = 18 \text{ inches} \times 0.0254 \text{ m/inch} = \mathbf{0.4572\text{m}}$$

$$\text{Width} = 16 \text{ inches} \times 0.0254 \text{ m/inch} = \mathbf{0.4064\text{m}}$$

$$\text{Thickness} = 3 \text{ inches} \times 0.0254 \text{ m/inch} = \mathbf{0.0762\text{m}}$$

$$\text{Volume (V)} = \text{Length (L)} \times \text{Width (W)} \times \text{Thickness (T)}$$

$$V = 0.4572\text{m} \times 0.4064\text{m} \times 0.0762\text{m} = \mathbf{0.01416 \text{ cubic meters}}$$

$$\text{Density} = \frac{0.95\text{kg}}{0.01416 \text{ cubic meters}} = \mathbf{67.09 \text{ kg/m}^3}$$

The density of a material is one of the determining factors in the effectiveness of an insulating material. Insulation materials work by reducing the rate of heat transfer, which is influenced by the material's density, among other factors. Also, materials with lower density value have better insulating properties than higher density value because lower density materials have more air pockets, which in turn traps heat thereby reducing heat experienced. In the density calculation above, we can say that our mycelium insulation is dense enough that it can help in the reduction of heat received and experienced.

Relationship of Density and Temperature

Density is one among the many factors that determine the effectiveness of an insulating material and as said earlier, lower density materials have more air pockets which traps heat and slows its movement. The resulting density (67.09 kg/m^3) suggests that its effective at reducing heat transfer and acts as a good insulator.

As stated in sage-advice.com, air in general is a good thermal insulator, but it can transmit heat through convection. However, if the air pockets inside the insulating material are separated from each other, heat flow from one air pocket to another cannot happen easily therefore reducing heat. In another article by *Dr. Energy Saver Home Services*, air pockets serve as a barrier that traps and slows down heat through conduction and convection between the object and its surroundings. On the same article, it was stated that just a 4% void in fiberglass batt insulation (absence of air pockets) can result in a 50% reduction in insulation effectiveness.

The fixed density of 67.09 kg/m^3 can be interpreted as effective because during the experiment we conducted, there was a significant difference between the temperature with a difference of $3\text{-}6^\circ\text{C}$, with it peaking at $7\text{-}8^\circ\text{C}$ in difference at times between the insulated box and the control box which is much greater than our assumption signifying that its effective at insulating.

Effect of Material Thickness in Temperature Reduction

Determined thickness during the study – **3 Inches**

In our study, we created and experimented with our mycelium-based insulation with a fixed thickness of 3 inches and monitored temperatures during our actual experimentation placing our mycelium insulation atop a customized box to evaluate its effect on temperature reduction compared to the control box which has no any insulation applied.

The fixed thickness resulted in a significant decrease in temperature. Data recorded at peak point of the day such as 12 PM shows significant difference between the temperature between the insulated and control box, the difference being greater than the 3-6°C assumption of our study. Through this data, we can safely assume that our mycelium effectively reduced heat inside the box providing reduced heat experienced. The insulation helped maintain cooler indoor temperatures than the outside temperature experiencing 49-50°C in temperature.

Temperature Effectiveness

To better prove the effectivity of the mycelium insulation, we also solved the heat index. Heat index is used to describe how hot it feels to the human body, rather than just the air temperature. It considers both air temperature and humidity. For the heat index, we compared the heat index for each day between the two boxes (Insulated box and the control box). The resulting heat index will help determine the heat index inside the boxes and also prove the effectiveness of mycelium-based insulation in reducing heat experienced.

As a point of reference, below is the Heat Index Observation table generated by the Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration is the National Meteorological and Hydrological Services, a government agency mandated to deliver reliable and relevant weather-related information.

Figure 16: PAGASA Heat Index Chart

Temperature Effectiveness through Heat Index

Day	Temperature	Dewpoint	Heat Index
Day 1 – 4/29/2024			
Insulated Box	38.4°C	22°C	44°C
Control Box	50.7°C	22°C	59°C
Day 2 – 4/30/2024			
Insulated Box	40.8°C	22°C	47°C
Control Box	42.5°C	22°C	49°C
Day 3 – 5/1/2024			
Insulated Box	35.4°C	22°C	40°C
Control Box	47.9°C	22°C	56°C

Table 5: Comparison Table representing the Heat Index Calculation between the Insulated Box and Control Box

Use Dew Point Temperature

Result

Heat Index Temperature: **53°C** (128°F or 327K)

Relative Humidity: 26%

Danger: at this condition, heat cramps and heat exhaustion are likely; heat stroke is probable with continued activity.

Figure 17: Heat Index calculator by calculator.net used in finding the heat index

Table 5 above shows the heat index calculations and compares the results taken from both insulated box and control box. Figure 21 on the other hand shows the calculator used to calculate the heat index. The temperature used in the calculator above is from the average temperature we got from the experimentation. On the other hand, the Dew point temperature is the temperature the air needs to be cooled to (at constant pressure) in order to achieve a relative humidity (RH) of 100% and we got the Dew Point temperature data from the daily weather bulletin posted by PAGASA or Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration. Dew point was used because this is what was required by the required to calculate the heat index.

We then compared the results and the results showed significant difference in heat index between the insulated and control box. The dew point was straight 22°C because for 3 days, it was very humid, and the dew point recorded by PAGASA was consistent. Based on the data recorded, it shows that the box applied with mycelium-based insulation consistently maintains a lower heat index compared to control box where there was not any insulation applied over the three-day period. For instance, on Day 1, the heat index of the insulated box is 44°C while the control box has a heat index of 53°C which has a difference of 9°C. On Day 2, the heat index of the insulated box is 48°C, while the control box has a heat index of 55°C which is a 7°C difference. And on Day 3, the heat index of the insulated box is 40°C, while the control box has a heat index of 52°C which is 12°C difference.

The difference in heat index suggests that the mycelium insulation is effective at reducing heat compared to the control box which has no insulation. Throughout the experiment, the insulated box was able to maintain a lower temperature than what the control box experienced which was very hot.

The resulting data presents as supporting point on the effectiveness of mycelium as an insulating material as it was able to maintain a lower heat index. By having a lower heat index, the mycelium insulation help alleviate heat in households and create a comfortable household temperature which is a key characteristic of an effective insulation.

CHAPTER V

Summary of Findings, Conclusion, and Recommendation

This chapter provides an overview of the results presented in the preceding chapter, summarizes the conclusions drawn from the summary, and offers recommendations derived from the analysis and interpretation of the data presented in the prior chapter.

Summary of Findings

Researchers conducted an experiment to explore the potential of using mycelium-based insulation panels made of oyster mushrooms, rice straw, and flour as additives. The panels were tested for their effectiveness in reducing temperature by comparing them to a control box without insulation. Temperature and humidity were monitored using a digital hygrometer/thermometer.

The results showed that the mycelium-based insulation panels successfully reduced temperatures by an average of 3-6°C, and in some cases, the reduction exceeded 7-8°C. The panels consistently maintained lower temperatures compared to the control box, demonstrating their effectiveness in reducing heat transfer.

Density calculations confirmed that the insulation was effective in reducing heat transfer. The mycelium-based insulation material had a density of 67 kg/m³, indicating that it minimized air pockets and reduced heat transfer.

The three-week monitoring of temperature and humidity provided insights into the growth conditions and their impact on mycelium and insulation performance. The temperature ranged from 30.1°C to 35.8°C, indicating varying conditions experienced by the mycelium. High temperatures, such as the recorded 35.8°C on April 24, potentially caused stress and hindered mycelium growth. On the other hand, humidity levels were consistently moist, ranging from 73% to 99%, which is favorable for mycelium growth.

However, there were some variations in humidity levels on certain days, such as April 23 and 24, where the humidity dropped to 78% and 73% respectively. These variations suggested that external factors, possibly weather patterns, influenced the humidity within

the mycelium panel mold. Managing temperature and humidity levels is crucial for optimizing mycelium growth and ensuring the long-term effectiveness of the insulation.

The observed temperatures generally fell within the optimal range for mycelium growth. However, higher temperatures like 35.8°C may have some negative effects as they promote the growth of competing bacteria. Despite this, the temperatures indicated favorable conditions for mycelium growth.

The mycelium-based insulation consistently maintained a lower heat index compared to the control box. The difference in heat index, ranging from 7°C to 12°C, highlighted the effectiveness of the mycelium insulation in reducing heat transfer and maintaining lower temperatures.

Overall, these findings suggest that mycelium-based insulation panels have the potential for household use. They effectively reduce temperatures, demonstrate suitable density for insulation, and maintain lower heat index values. Managing temperature and humidity levels is crucial for optimizing mycelium growth and ensuring the long-term effectiveness of the insulation.

Conclusion

This research study was mainly focused on finding or discovering the benefits and possibility of producing a of mycelium-based insulation material. The overall study aligns with Fellah et al. (2024), highlighting mycelium's versatility, affordability, and eco-friendliness. Through a series of experiments and analysis, the researchers demonstrated the potential of mycelium-based insulation as a sustainable and effective alternative as insulation material. The significant temperature differences recorded between the insulated and control boxes underscore the effectiveness of mycelium in reducing heat transfer. Moreover, this research contributes to addressing the challenges of climate change by offering an innovative and environmentally friendly solution to the issues of energy efficiency and sustainable construction practices. Given the rising temperatures caused by the depletion of the ozone layer and increased air pollution, exploring alternative insulation materials is crucial.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

Government. To allocate sufficient budget to concerned government agencies such as the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) and Department of Science and Technology (DOST) to buy equipment that can help different researchers to conduct tests on their creations. Our group believes that such limitations hinder the development of different potential world-changing products made by creative Filipino minds.

Homeowners. To explore the utilization of mycelium insulation in their respective households. The mycelium-based insulation panel could be also be beneficial to those families who are short on money to buy effective construction materials for their homes. The mycelium insulation can also be beneficial to provinces in the country that experiences high heat index where indoor temperature isn't comfortable for a human to be in.

Urban Planners. To further study the possible inclusion of mycelium insulation into buildings which can contribute to the development of sustainable communities. Urban planners can help in the green building advocacies where they can promote the usage and exploration in utilizing mycelium insulation to create sustainable building practices within communities.

Future Researchers. To further optimized the properties of the mycelium insulation we've created and further study its long-term potential. Future researchers can also use the study as a reference to create their own mycelium insulation, taking notes from the study conducted. Future Researches can also explore other scope to further improve the potential of the product and utilized in different conditions.

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Appendix C: Photo Documentation of the Actual Experimentation and Product making

Below shows the general overview of the production process of the mycelium-based insulation panel from the Conceptualization stage to the Final product. The entire process is outlined in Phases.

Phase 1: Development Process and Visualization of the Product

Phase 2: Mould/Panel creation

Phase 3: Pasteurization of Rice Straw

Phase 4: Panel assembly and spawn planting

Phase 5: Drying Process

Phase 6: Creation of experimentation box

Phase 7: Actual Experimentation

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